

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№ 10

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

*Elektron nashr. 1836 sahifa.
2025-yil, 31-oktyabr*

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate

Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society

Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor

Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor

Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor

Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)

Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)

Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan

Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan

Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences

Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer

Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor

Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)

Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)

Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow))

Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE

Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI

Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Khusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Rakhimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI YASHIL ENERGIYA: BARCHA UCHUN MUHIM MASALA.....	13
Muxiddin Kalonov	
MOLIYAVIY INNOVATSIYALAR: IQTISODIY MOHIYATI, QO‘LLANILISHI VA RIVOJLANISHI.....	19
Quliyev Begimqul Melikovich	
SAVDO KORXONALARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA STATISTIK TAHLIL USULLARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING AHAMIYATI.....	24
Sabirova Oysuluv Shonazarovna	
KORXONANING MEBEL MAXSULOTLARI BOZORIDAGI O‘RNINI KENGAYTIRISH USULLARI	30
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INVESTITSIYA KO‘RSATKICHLARI TIZIMINING FUNKSIONAL JIHATI.....	35
Alabayev Sobitxon	
MAMLAKATIMIZDA MAHSULOTLARNING MUVOFIQLIGINI BAHOLASH AMALIYOTI.....	40
Zakirov Ansabxon Akaidinovich	
ПЕСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЁНЫХ ОБЛИГАЦИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	48
Саидахмедова Аида Мирзаевна	
KORXONALAR FAOLIYATIDA DEBITOR VA KREDITOR QARZDORLIKNI BOSHQARISH	55
Mirzayev Ozod Furkatovich	
AHOLI PUL DAROMADLARI VA HUDUDIY IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISH KO‘RSATKICHLARI O‘RTASIDAGI EKONOMETRIK TAHLIL.....	59
Qodirov Farrux Ergash o‘g‘li	
BUDJET RESURSLARI SHAKLLANISHIDA HUDUDNING SOLIQ SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH VA MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIK.....	64
Yuldashev Adhamjon Axadjonovich	
SANOAT KORXONALARI IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHI TUSHUNCHASIGA NAZARIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	69
Muydinov Xusniddin Nuriddin o‘g‘li	
МЕТОДИКА УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫМИ ПОТОКАМИ В СИСТЕМЕ УПРАВЛЕНЧЕСКОГО УЧЕТА	73
Минутдинова Лилия Тагировна, Машарипов Озод Алимович	
ГАРМОНИЗАЦИЯ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН В СООТВЕТСТВИИ С МСФО	78
Абдужалилова Дилноз Абдусаттаровна	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA SMART TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING DOLZARBLIGI.....	84
Sobirjonov Muxiddin Toxirjon o‘g‘li	
TO‘LOVGA QOBILIYATSIZLIK HOLATIDAGI KORXONALARDA TUGATISH BALANSINI TUZISH.....	90
Nabiyev Gofurjon Nosirjon o‘g‘li	
O‘ZBEKISTON SANOATINING “YASHIL” IQTISODIYOTGA O‘TAYOTGANLIGI: IMKONIYATLAR VA CHEKLOVLAR	96
Habibullayev Oybek Asliddin o‘g‘li	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT KONTSEPTSIYASINING EVOLYUTSIYASI VA ILMIY-NAZARIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	102
Allayarov Suxrob Rustamovich	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA TO‘G‘RIDAN-TO‘G‘RI CHET EL INVESTITSIYALARINING MILLIY IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDAGI ROLI	107
Raxmatov Adxam Itolmasovich, Boynazarova Matluba Xatamovna	

HUDUDIY IJTIMOY TENGLIK VA KAMBAG'ALLIKNI YUMSHATISHDA MEHNAT RESURSLARI OMILLARI.....	114
Durumov Temur G'olibovich	
TRANSPORT TARMOG'I VA MILLIY IQTISODIYOTNING ASOSIY TARMOQLARI O'RTASIDAGI BOG'LIQLIKNI MODELASHTIRISH (SURXANDARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	121
Turayev Baxtiyor Ergashevich, Aymatov Sirojiddin To'raqul o'g'li	
РОЛЬ ЭНЕРГЕТИКИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РОСТА ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	134
Нигматуллаева Гулчехра Нуруллаевна	
O'ZBEKISTONDA OLIY TA'LIM BOZORINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENTSIYALARI VA UNDA SIFAT MENEJMENTINING ROLI.....	139
Yuldashev Iskandar Bahromovich	
YER QA'RIDAN FOYDALANUVCHILARGA SOLIQ SOLISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	145
Zoxidov Ismatjon Yunusjon o'g'li	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA TURIZM INDUSTRIYASIDA INNOVATSION BIZNES-MODELLAR.....	151
Shaxinabonu Choriyeva	
AVTOTRANSPORT – EKSPEDITSIYA XIZMATLARI BOZORIDA MARKETING KONTSEPSIYASI.....	157
Ergasheva Mukhabbat Abdusamatovna	
“YASHIL” ENERGIYA ISHLAB CHIQRUVCHI KICHIK TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARINI SOLIQQA TORTISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI	163
Toshemirov To'liqin Toirjonovich	
DAVLAT IQTISODIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA SIYOSIY INSTITUTLARNING ROLI VA UNI KUCHAYTIRISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	166
O. Nurmuradov	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA RAQAMLI BANK TEXNOLOGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ASOSLARI	171
Meyliqulov Shaxboz Xolmamat o'g'li	
СВЯЗНОСТЬ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ И РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫХ СТРАТЕГИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ.....	176
Ташматов Гайрат Ровшанович, Содиков Авазбек Мадаминович	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASI TURIZM SOHASINI RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA RIVOJLANTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	183
Zarikeyeva Miyasar Maratovna	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYASI.....	187
Saidrahmatova Zuhraxon Saidazim qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON KONCHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARIDA INVESTITSION JARAYONLARNI BOSHQARISH VA INNOVATSION XAVFLARNI KAMAYTIRISH STRATEGIYALARI	192
Kurbanova Mehriniso Nematjanovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA QULAY INVESTITSIYA MUHITINI SHAKLLANTIRISH MUAMMOLARI.....	196
Xuramov Zafar Rajabaliyevich	
PAHTA-TO'QIMACHILIK KLASTERLARIDA XOMASHYO TA'MINOTI BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING XORIJ DAVLATLAR TAJRIBASI.....	201
Zakirov Abduazim Abdurashidovich	
НОВЫЙ ЭТАП ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ РЫНОЧНЫХ МЕХАНИЗМОВ В ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ.....	206
Махкамов Ибраим	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SUG'URTA BOZORINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENTSIYALARI.....	213
Xushmuradov Oman, Ismoilov Sherzod Ismoil o'g'li	
GLOBALIZATSIYA SHAROITIDA MILLIY IQTISODIYOT NAZARIYASI.....	217
Mo'ydinov Xurshidbek Abdullayevich	
DORIVOR O'SIMLIKLARNI QAYTA ISHLASHNING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA MUAMMOLARI	221
Usmonov Mirg'ulom Xoshim o'g'li	

BARQAROR IQTISODIY O‘SISHGA YERISHISHDA SUN’IY INTELLEKT TIZIMLARINI QO‘LLASH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILASHTIRISH (XORIJIY DAVLATLAR TAJRIBASI MISOLIDA)	227
Nasrulloev Hayotjon Xabibulloevich	
НЕЙРОИНТУИТИВНЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ И ЕГО РОЛЬ В УПРАВЛЕНИИ РИСКАМИ В БИЗНЕСЕ.....	233
Ягудин Дмитрий Рустамович	
RESURLARNI SOLIQQA TORTISH AMALIYOTINING XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI VA ULARNING MILLIY SOLIQQA TIZIMIDA QO‘LLASH MASALALARI	240
Nasimdjanoov Yunusjon Zoxidovich	
O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA KICHIK TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARI UCHUN QO‘LLANILAYOTGAN SOLIQQA TORTISH MEKANIZMLARI	246
Akbarov Akramjon Ibragimzhonovich	
TO‘QIMACHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARIDA “YASHIL” MARKETINGNI JORIY ETISHNING DOLZARB JIHATLARI	250
Bazarova Fayyoza Tuxtamurodovna	
INSON KAPITALI VA IQTISODIYOTNING RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYASI.....	255
Muzaffar Raximov	
UY-JOY KOMMUNAL XO‘JALIGINI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI.....	259
Odamboyev Oybek Ravshanbek o‘g‘li	
INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS’ APPROACHES TO ATTRACTING INVESTMENT IN HUMAN CAPITAL	268
Akhmadaliyeva Nikholakhon	
RAQAMLI PLATFORMALAR ORQALI KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO‘LLARI.....	273
Vohobov Hikmatillo Ma‘mirjon o‘g‘li	
ФОРСАЙТ И ЭКОНОМИЧНЫЕ ИННОВАЦИИ КАК ДРАЙВЕРЫ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ТОРГОВЛИ САМАРКАНДА	280
Тохилова Гуллола Миркамоловна	
KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNI BOSHQARISHDA KASB-HUNAR TA‘LIMI BITIRUVCHILARINING O‘RNI	287
Toshpulatov Sherzod Xaydarkulovich	
DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN ECOTOURISM: INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES FOR ADVANCING GREEN TOURISM.....	292
Barno Erkayeva	
AGROTURIZM SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	296
Baymuradova Iroda Shermamatovna, Mardonova Zarifa Numonjonovna	
DAVLAT BUDJET NAZORATI TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO‘NALISHLARI	301
B.Sh.Mirzayev	
YOSHLAR BANDLIGIDA KO‘NIKMALAR NOMUTANOSIBLIGI MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI.....	307
Rahmatxo‘jayev Axrorxo‘ja Akmal o‘g‘li	
TO‘QIMACHILIK MAHSULOTLARINING EKSPORT SALOHİYATINI TAHLIL QILISH VA RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARINI BAHOLASH.....	311
Oqboyev Alisher Rasuljanovich	
РЕИНЖИНИРИНГ БИЗНЕС-ПРОЦЕССОВ И ИХ РОЛЬ В РАЗВИТИИ БАНКОВСКОГО БИЗНЕСА.....	317
Рахимходжаева Нодира Саидахраловна	
QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGI TA‘MINOT ZANJIRI JARAYONLARINING HOZIRGI HOLATINI TAHLIL QILISH.....	323
Ermonov Farrux	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNI SHAKILLANTIRISH JARAYONIDA MOLIVAVIY NAZORATNI INNOVATSION TA‘LIM YO‘NALISHLARINI YO‘LGA QO‘YISH ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO‘LLARI.....	329
Turg‘unov Bahtiyor Nuriddinovich	

MARKAZIY OSIYODA SUV RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISH VA HAMKORLIKNING DOLZARB MASALALARI	334
Amanbaev Amanali Orazbaevich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA YANGI TURDAGI LOGISTIKA XIZMATLARINING USLUBIY ASOSLARI.....	338
Z. Teshayev	
O'ZBEKISTON AXBOROT-KOMMUNIKATSIYA XIZMATLARI SOHASINING AMALDAGI HOLATINI TAHLIL QILISH.....	343
Suyunov Asror Baxtiyorovich	
KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVDA LEADERSHIP 4.0 TAMOYILLARINI JORIY ETISH SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	349
Ismailov Allayor Rashidovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA AHOLI BANDLIGINI TA'MINLASH MASALALARI.....	355
Yusupov Farxod Adamboyevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI O'RNI VA UNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNI USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI	359
Abdullaeva Nilufar Javdat qizi	
MINTAQADA SANOAT KORXONALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING SOLISHTIRMA EKONOMETRIK MODELLARI (SURXONDARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	363
Saatmurotov Shohrux Zafar o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON SUG'URTA BOZORI: RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI VA ISTIQBOLLI IMKONIYATLAR	369
Abdurazaqov Jasur Abdunasimovich	
RAQAMLI PLATFORMALAR YORDAMIDA NORASMIY VA YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNI QISQARTIRISHNING QO'SHIMCHA IMKONIYATLARI TO'G'RSIDA.....	374
Nasrullayev Hikmatullo Habibulloyevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA KICHIK VA O'RTA BIZNESNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH MAQSADIDA "XIZMATLAR IPOTEKASI" MOLIYAVIY INSTRUMENTLARINI AMALIYOTGA JORIY QILISH MASALALARI	379
Uskenbayeva Dilnoza Boxodir qizi	
ЭКОНОМИКО-СТАТИСТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ КАПЕЛЬНОГО ОРОШЕНИЯ ПРИ ВОЗДЕЛЫВАНИИ ЛУКА В ДЖИЗАКСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ.....	384
Суюнов Шохзодбек Мурод угли	
XORIJIY DAVLATLAR SANOAT IQTISODIYOTIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH TAJRIBASI (YAPONIYA, KOREYA VA GERMANIYA MISOLIDA)	389
Mansurova Sayyora Baxtiyor Kizi	
KORXONALARDA ISHLAB CHIQRARISH XARAJATLARI HISOBGA OLIHDA XORIY TAJRIBASINI QO'LLASH	395
Raxmatov Baxriddin Baxtiyor o'g'li	
PECULIARITIES OF THE IRRIGATION WATER DELIVERY PAYMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	399
Muminov Sherzod Kholmiraevich	
DIGITALIZATION OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS FOR EXPORT	404
Azimov R.B.	
AHOLI JON BOSHIGA UMUMIY DAROMADLAR HAJMINI TREND MODELLAR ASOSIDA PROGNOZLASH	409
Xolto'rayev Islom Ilhomovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA YANGI BANDLIK SHAKLLARI	416
Sayipov Begzod Rahimovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING YANGI DAVR SHAROITIDA MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI BAHOLASH USULLARI VA INDIKATORLARI	422
Sadikov Iskandar Gayratovich	

MAHALLIY BUDJET SOLIQLI DAROMADLARI BAZASI BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA SOLIQLAR TA'SIRCHANLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	433
<i>Isoqov Zafarjon Zokirjonovich</i>	
TOSHKENT SHAHRIDAGI YIRIK SOLIQ TO'LOVCHILARNING SOLIQ QARZDORLIGI TAHLILI	438
<i>Soipov Boburmirzo Nosirjon o'g'li</i>	
РОЛЬ ЖИЛИЩНОЙ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРЫ В СИСТЕМЕ КОМПЛЕКСНОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ТЕРРИТОРИЙ МЕЗОУРОВНЯ.....	446
<i>Далиев Ахтам Шарафудинович</i>	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOAT KORXONALARIDA INSON RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISHDA XORIJ TAJRIBALARINING ZARURLIGI.....	454
<i>Abdullayev Dostonbek G'ofurjon o'g'li</i>	
TURISTIK KLASTERLARNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA ULARNING HUDUDIY IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDAGI O'RNI	458
<i>Xaitov Oxunjon Nomoz o'g'li</i>	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA RESURS TA'MINOTI BOSHQARUVINING NAZARIY KONSEPSIYALARI VA MODELLARI.....	462
<i>Arziqulova Oybar chin Eshquvat qizi</i>	
XIZMATLAR SEKTORIDA RAQAMLI INNOVATSIYALAR VA MIJOZLAR EHTIYOJLARINI QONDIRISH MEKANIZMLARI	467
<i>Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich</i>	
СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКАЯ СУЩНОСТЬ ПОДГОТОВКИ КАДРОВ В РАЗВИТИИ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА.....	472
<i>Базаров Бердымурад Улугмуродович, Атавуллаева Саида Джумабекмуродовна</i>	
TURIZM SOHASIDA KADRLAR SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISHNING TASHKILIY-IQTISODIY MEKANIZMI.....	478
<i>Xo'jaqulov Bobur Rustam o'g'li</i>	
KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA DAVLATNING RO'LI	483
<i>Nabiyeva Muxabbat Djabirxanovna</i>	
"HOW GREEN INVESETMENTS CAN EFFECT ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES"	485
<i>Farangiz Ma'rufjonovna Pirmatova</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA UZOQ MUDDATLI RESURSLAR MANBALARI VA ULARNING HAJMINI OSHIRISHNING ZARURIYATI.....	493
<i>Abduraxmonov Akmal Nurmat o'g'li</i>	
GLOBAL BOSHQARUV VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHDA YASHIL TEXNOLOGIYALARNING ROLI	498
<i>M.Sh. Tolipov</i>	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕХАНИЗМОВ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВОЙ УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКИХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ	504
<i>Буранбаева Шоира Рустамовна</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA PIYOZ YETISHTIRISHDA TOMCHILATIB SUG'ORISHNI QO'LLASH ISTIQBOLLARI	508
<i>Suyunov Shohzodbek Murod o'g'li</i>	
YENGIL SANOAT KORXONALARINING RIVOJLANISHIGA BOSHQARUV MADANIYATIDAN FOYDALANISHNING TA'SIRI.....	513
<i>Aknazarova Zebiniso Bagdadovna</i>	
ISHLAB CHIQRISHNI DIVERSIFIKATSIYALASH SHAROITIDA KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVNING TASHKILIY-IQTISODIY MEKANIZM SAMARADORLIGINI ANIQLASH USULLARI	518
<i>Qurbaniyazov Shaxzodbek Karimovich</i>	
KICHIK BIZNESNI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA JOYLASHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY VA TASHKILIY ASOSLARI	524
<i>Salimov Burxon Abubakirovich</i>	
"YASHIL" IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA UNDA ENERGIYADAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	530
<i>Berdiyeva Aziza G'anisher qizi</i>	

SIRKULAR IQTISODIYOTDAN KORXONA VA TADBIRKORLAR MANFAATLARI	535
Sodikov Zokir Rustamovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK SOHASIDA ME'YORIY-HUQUQIY BAZANI ISHLAB CHIQISH.....	541
Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich, Ubaydullayev Toxirjon Abdullajanovich	
MINTAQA OZIQ-OVQAT MAHSULOTLARI CHAKANA SAVDOSIDA SHADOW WAREHOUSE MODELIGA ASOSLANGAN YETKAZIB BERISH TIZIMINI JORIY QILISH.....	548
Ibrayimova Dilnoza Abdisherpovna	
XIZMATLAR SAVDOSI SOHASIDA O'ZBEKISTONNING XALQARO HAMKORLIK IMKONIYATLARI	555
Qodirjonov A.M.	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATINI IQTISODIY RIVOJLANTIRISHDA RESURLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH KONSEPSIYASINI SHAKLLANTIRISH USLUBIYOTI.....	559
Madraximova Gulasal Ro'zimboy qizi	
ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ ТРЕНДЫ СМАРТ-ТУРИЗМА И ИХ ПРИМЕНИМОСТЬ К КУЛЬТУРНОМУ НАСЛЕДИЮ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	564
Салихбаев Нурсултон Равшанович	
IJTIMOIIY NIHOYA TIZIMI VA IJTIMOIIY TIBBIY XIZMATLAR O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIGINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	572
Shanazarov Farrux Shodiyorovich	
ТЕХНИКО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЕ ОБОСНОВАНИЕ РАЗРАБОТКИ МОБИЛЬНОГО ПРИЛОЖЕНИЯ JOB VARAKA ДЛЯ РЫНКА ТРУДА УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	577
Еримбетова Улбосын Маратовна	
TASHQI SAVDO VA INVESTITSIYALAR TAHLILI HAMDA ULARNING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKKA TA'SIRI.....	582
Jalolov Bekzod Sherzod o'g'li	
“O'ZBEKISTONDA KICHIK VA O'RTA BIZNESLAR UCHUN SUN'IY INTELLEKT ASOSIDA MOLIYAVIY KO'RSATKICHLARNI TAHLIL QILISH VA RAQAMLI YECHIMLAR TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH”	586
Azamatjon Mardayev Abdusamat o'g'li	
FARMATSEVIKA MAHSULOTLARI ISHLAB CHIQARUVCHI KORXONALARDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINI TASHKIL ETISHNING ME'YORIY-HUQUQIY ASOSLARI.....	591
Xudaynazarova Dilnoza Gafurovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INNOVASION TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA KADRLAR TAYYORLASH MENEJMENTINING AMAL QILISH USULLARI VA TURLARI	596
Ergashev To'liqin Shokirovich	
HUDUDIIY IQTISODIYOTNI RAQAMLI TEKNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	602
Ibragimov Baxrom Baxodirovich	
ISLOMIY MOLIYA INSTRUMENTLARINI JORIY ETISH ORQALI O'ZBEKISTONDA MOLIYA BOZORINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISHNING STRATEGIK YO'NALISHLARI.....	606
Xodjayev Aziz Shovkatovich	
MAHALLIY HOKIMIYAT QAROR QABUL QILISH JARAYONLARIDA DINAMIK OMILLAR VA ULARNING INTEGRATSIYASI	611
Axmedov Farxod Raxmonjonovich	
UZOQ MUDDATLI AKTIVLAR AUDITINI TASHKIL ETISH VA TAHLIL QILISH METODLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	617
Rizakulov Abdurauf Abdimutalibovich	
ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ПРИВЛЕКАТЕЛЬНОСТИ ТУРИЗМА ЧЕРЕЗ КРЕАТИВНУЮ ИНДУСТРИЮ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН.....	623
Хошимова Камилла Навфал қизи	
IMITATION MODELDA AXBOROT NORAVSHANLIGI SABABLI YUZAGA KELADIGAN IQTISODIY SAMARASIZLIK TAHLILI.....	633
Qodirov Zohidjon Eralievich	

JISMONIY SHAXSLAR TOMONIDAN KREDITLARDAN FOYDALANISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI	637
Turdiyeva Kumush Erkinovna	
SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH XIZMATLARI SOHASIDA SIFATNI BAHOLASH KO'RSATKICHLARI VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIK O'RTASIDAGI BOG'LIQLIK.....	641
Usmanova Nasiba Akbarjonovna, Eshbekova Xayriniso Baxtiyorovna	
SOLIQ TO'LOVCHILAR FAOLIYATINING SEGMENTATSIYASIGA ASOSLANIB SOLIQ XAVFLARINI ANIQLASH VA BAHOLASHNING AMALIY YONDOSHUVI	648
Elbaeva M.R.	
DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHGA TA'SIRI.....	653
Hamroyev G'ayratjon Sultonovich	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISHNI SIFAT MENEJMENTI TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA TASHKIL ETISHNING XORIJ MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI	657
Achilov Ilmurad	
MINTAQALAR INVESTITSION SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISHNING NAZARIY VA METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	663
Qobilov Anvar Eshpo'lotovich	
KORXONALARNING YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYASINI ISHLAB CHIQISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	669
Sapayev Axmed Durdibayevich	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASHDA KO'P MEZONLI TAHLIL USULLARINI QO'LLASH.....	674
Muxammadaliyev Mirzohidjon Muxammadali o'g'li	
BOJXONA HUDUDIDA QAYTA ISHLASH BOJXONA REJIMINING AMALDAGI HOLATI TAHLILI	681
Abdullayev Shaxzodbek	
ENSURING SUSTAINABLE REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT THROUGH INTEGRATION OF RECREATION AND ECOTOURISM RESOURCES IN UZBEKISTAN	686
Shaymanova Nigora Yusupovna	
MAKROIQTISODIYOTDA ISTE'MOL VA JAMG'ARISH FUNSIYALARI VA ULARNING O'ZBEKISTONDA O'ZGARISHI TENDENSIYALARI	691
Rustamov Narzillo Istamovich	
CHAKANA SAVDONI BOSHQARISHDA "BIG MIDDLE" NAZARIYASIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	697
Yaqubov Azizbek G'anibekovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA HUNARMANDCHILIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PROGNOZ VARIANTLARI.....	701
Ermetov Amirbek Ismailovich	
FISKAL NOMARKAZLASHTIRISH BO'YICHA XITOIY TAJRIBASI.....	708
Lokayev Bekzod Sherkobilovich	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA RAQAMLI BOSHQARUV TIZIMLARI: IMKONIYATLAR VA CHEKLOVLAR.....	712
Ismatullayeva Munisxon Bori qizi	
EKOLOGIYA VA ATROF MUHITNI MUHOFAZA QILISH SOHASIDA DASTURIY BUDJETLASHTIRISH BO'YICHA XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI.....	717
Dilshod Pulatov, Dildora Mirzaeva, Gulzora Qahharova	
TIKUV-TRIKOTAJ SANOATIDA MEHNAT UNUMDORLIGINI OSHIRISH OMILLARI VA BOSHQARUV STRATEGIYALARI.....	725
Mardiyev Bunyod Sirojiddin o'g'li	
BURNOUTNING OLDINI OLIH: XODIMLAR SALOMATLIGI STRATEGIYASI.....	731
Ergasheva E'zoza Dilshod qizi	
O'ZBEKISTONDA KORXONALARNING TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA MUAMMOLARI.....	736
Pulatova Moxira Baxtiyorovna	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI KORXONALARIDA XARAJATLARNI BOSHQARISH VA HISOBGA OLIHNING INNOVATSION USULLARI: MENEJMENT VA BUXGALTERIYANING O'ZARO INTEGRATSIYASI.....	742
Mamadiyarov Dilshad Uralovich, Normurodov Sarvar Norboy o'g'li	

RIVOJLANGAN MAMLAKATLARDA AHOLI DAROMADLARINI OSHIRISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	748
Uzoqov Suhrobjon Do'smat o'g'li	
OLIY TA'LIMNI MOLIYALASHTIRISH MODELLARI.....	754
Talapova Nargiza Baxriddinovna	
ВОЗОБНОВЛЕНИЕ ДОБЫЧИ ПРИРОДНОГО ГАЗА ИЗ ТРЁХ СКВАЖИН УЧАСТКА ХОДЖАСАЯТ ГКМ ДЕНГИЗКУЛЬ.....	758
Набиев Шахзод Темурович, Иргашбаев Шохрух Фаррух угли, Маннафов Улугбек Умар угли	
MADANIY TURIZM INDUSTRIYASINING RIVOJLANISH IMKONIYATLARI VA O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI.....	764
Toxirov Dilyor Davlatovich	
MOLIYAVIY AUTSORSING NAZARIYALARI VA UNING RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI.....	768
Babadjanov Umidbek Kamildjanovich	
TURIZM – TARIXIY XOTIRA VA ZAMONAVIY XIZMATLAR UYG'UNLIGI IFODASI.....	773
Janzakov Bekzot Kulmamat o'g'li	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINING MOHIYATI VA BAHOLASH MEZONLARI.....	777
Abdikarimova Zilola Baxramovna	
TIJORAT BANKLARI AKTIVLARINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYALASHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	784
Ro'ziyeva Shaxlo Salimboyevna	
AXBOROT TIZIMLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA TEXNIK XIZMAT KO'RSATISHNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH.....	788
Samiyeva Maftuna Faxriddin qizi	
TIJORAT BANKLARI AKTIVLARI DAROMADLILIGINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI.....	791
Sanayev Javoxir Shovkat o'g'li	
FISCAL, MONETARY, AND CUSTOMS-TARIFF POLICIES IN ENSURING NATIONAL ECONOMIC STABILITY: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN.....	796
Maxmudov S.T.	
ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ И РАЗВИТИЯ ТУРИСТИЧЕСКИХ КЛАСТЕРОВ.....	801
Юсупова Н.Т.	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY O'SISHIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI ASOSIY FAKTORLAR TAHLILI.....	807
Rahimova Mushtariybegim Muxammadg'olib qizi	
DEMOGRAFIK O'ZGARISHLAR VA ULARNING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY OQIBATLARI.....	812
Abdumalikova G.F.	
MINTAQAVIY INVESTITSIYA SIYOSATINI SAMARALI BOSHQARISHNING IQTISODIY VA INSTITUTSION ASOSLARI.....	821
Kenjayev Ikrom Ergashboyevich	
RAQAMLI AVIATSIYA EKOTIZIMI: AI/ML, DIGITAL TWIN VA BLOKCHEYN INTEGRATSIYASI.....	828
Azimova Moxinur Nozimovna	
XALQARO MOLIYA BOZORLARIDA INVESTITSIYA RISKLARINI BOSHQARISHNING ZAMONAVIY MEKANIZMLARI.....	834
G'afurov Sherzod Abduvaxob o'g'li	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATINING REKREATSIYA RESURLARI VA DAVOLASH-SOG'LOMLASHTIRISH TURIZMI SALOHIYATI.....	839
Murtazayeva Gulrux Isabek qizi	
MINTAQALAR TURISTIK-REKREATSION IMKONIYATLARINI BAHOLASHDA ZAMONAVIY GIS USULLARINI QO'LLASH (SARIOSIYO TUMANI MISOLIDA).....	845
Safarov Manuchexr Axtam o'g'li	
XITOIY TAJRIBASI ASOSIDA INVESTITSIYA MUHITINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	852
Tirkashev Farruxjon Xolyigitovich	
TURIZM FAOLIYATINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISHGA OID NAZARIY BILIMLARNING SHAKLLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI.....	857
Maxmudova Aziza Pirmamatovna	

TIJORAT BANKLARI RESURS BAZASI MUSTAHKAMLIGINI BAHOLOVCHI KO'RSATKICHLAR TIZIMI	863
Raxmanov Iloxom Xurramovich	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARIDA BOSHQARUV TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	871
Maxsudov Sherzod Solijonovich	
FISCAL, MONETARY, AND CUSTOMS-TARIFF POLICIES IN ENSURING NATIONAL ECONOMIC STABILITY: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN.....	877
Mahmudov Sarvar	
ATROF-MUHITGA OID FISKAL KO'RSATKICHLAR ASOSIDA MINTAQAVIY BAHOLASH	882
Zilola Rahmatova	
XORAZM VILOYATI TUMANLARIDA EKSPORT SAMARADORLIGI: STOXAСТИK CHEGARAVIY TAHLIL (SFA) ASOSIDAGI EMPIRIK YONDASHUV	887
Fozil Xolmurotov	
МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ОЦЕНКИ БЕДНОСТИ: МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ И НАЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ СПЕЦИФИКА.....	900
Мамаризоев Жахонгир Исохонович	
EKOLOGIK VAZIYAT VA AHOLI SALOMATLIGINING PROGNOZ KO'RSATKICHLARI	905
Egamqulov Husniddin Erkaboyevich	
CHO'L HUDUDLARIDA TURISTIK RESURLARDAN FOYDALANISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	911
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Mavlonov Ahmadjon Muhammadovich	
КОНЦЕПЦИЯ ИДЕНТИФИКАЦИИ И ИЗМЕРЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТОВ ЗАНЯТОСТИ В ЭКОЛОГО-ОРИЕНТИРОВАННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ.....	918
Сагидуллин Фарид Радикович	
ТЕНДЕНЦИИ В РАЗВИТИИ ГОСТИНИЧНОГО БИЗНЕСА В СФЕРЕ ПРОДВИЖЕНИЯ И СБЫТА ТОВАРОВ И УСЛУГ В ИНДУСТРИИ ГОСТЕПРИИМСТВА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН	927
Бабаджанова Лола Шопулатовна	
O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTIDA OZIQ-OVQATNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGINING ROLI.....	935
G'aniyev Baydulla Toshmurodovich, Bustonov Komiljon Kumakovich	
TURISTIK MINTAQALARNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA MAHALLIY AHOLINING ISHTIROKINI TA'MINLASHNING AYRIM MASALALARI	943
Abduxamidov Sarvar Adxamovich	
TA'LIM KLASTERLARI KONTEKSTIDA BOSHQARUVNING ZAMONAVIY MUAMMOLARI VA STRATEGIK YECHIMLARI: TRIPLE HELIX MODEL ASOSIDA TAHLIL.....	947
Imamova Nilufar Asamutdinovna	
EKOLOGIK TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY ASOSLARI VA ISTIQBOLLARI.....	954
Xamdullayeva Gulhoyo Ergash qizi	
TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI BAHOLASHNING USLUBIY YONDASHUVLARI	960
Sirojiddinov Kamoliddin	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	967
Seytimbetov Kabul Serimbetovich	
AGROTADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINING ASOSIY FUNKSIYALARI VA RIVOJLANISH QONUNIYATLARI.....	971
Nasriddinov Xusanbek Sadriddin o'g'li	
TEMIR YO'L TRANSPORTIDA ENERGIYA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH: QAYTA TIKLANADIGAN ENERGIYA MANBALARI	976
Abdusattorov Abdusamat Sobirovich	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA RESURLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH VA OZIQ-OVQAT MAHSULOTLARINI ISHLAB CHIQRISHDA MENEJMENT QARORLARINING IQTISODIY TAHLILI	981
Karieva Gulnora Abdullayevna, Normurodov Sarvar Norboy o'g'li	
TA'LIM TIZIMINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA O'QUV DASTURLARINING KAPITAL ZICHLIGI	989
Dusanov Salim Mamarasulovich	

QATTIQ CHIQUINDILARNI QAYTA ISHLASH KORXONALARIDA INNOVATSION MENEJMENTNING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI.....	995
Temirov Azizbek Voit o'g'li	
STRATEGIK REJALASHTIRISH ORQALI KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	1002
G.Ya. Muxibova, O.U. Sharifxodjayeva, O. To'rabekova	
ДЕТЕРМИНАНТЫ И ПОСЛЕДСТВИЯ МЕЖРЕГИОНАЛЬНОЙ МОБИЛЬНОСТИ РАБОЧЕЙ СИЛЫ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	1009
Шакаров Зафар Гаффорович	
TURIZM KLASTERLARIDA TIBBIY XIZMATLAR INTEGRATSIYASI: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTON AMALIYOTI	1018
Yazdanova Shohista Tuyg'un qizi, Farxodova Shohnoza Umidbek qizi	
TELEKOMMUNIKATSIYA SOHASI KORXONALARINING INNOVATSION FAOLLIGINI OSHIRUVCHI ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVNI ISHLAB CHIQUISH	1027
Xojiyeva Nazokat Davronbekovna	
QAYTA TIKLANADIGAN ENERGIYA MANBALARINING BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI: O'ZBEKISTON MISOLIDA.....	1034
Shodiyeva Zarinnabonu Shodi qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATIDA KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING ISTIQBOLLI YO'NALISHLARI.....	1039
Qurbaniyozov Shaxzodbek Karimovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA HISOB SIYOSATINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI	1044
Qurbanbayev Jurabek Eruvboyevich	
FINTECH TEXNOLOGIYALARI VA ULARNING KORXONA LIKVIDLIGIGA TA'SIRI.....	1048
Karimov Xondamir Jamshid o'g'li	
IMPROVING STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING OF INCOME AND EXPENSES.....	1056
Pardaeva Shakhnoza Abdinabievna	
DIGITAL SKILLS AND ACCOUNTING EDUCATION: NEEDS AND GAPS IN UZBEK HIGHER EDUCATION – CURRICULUM IMPLICATIONS FOR THE DIGITAL AGE	1061
Rustamova Iroda Bahtiyorovna	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING KREDIT XIZMATLARI: ZAMONAVIY TAHLIL VA TARAQQIYOT TENDENSIYALARI.....	1066
Jo'rayeva Zarifa Bahodir qizi	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI KORXONALARINING YUQORI SIFATLI RIVOJLANISHINI TA'MINLASH	1073
Yaxshiyev Shahzod Sherali o'g'li	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH	1079
Kuvotova Dilnora Kaxramonovna	
MAHSULOT, ISH (XIZMAT)LAR TANNARXIGA KIRITILADIGAN MODDIY XARAJATLAR VA ULARNI HUJJATLASHTIRISH.....	1084
Bolibekov Baxtiyor Achilovich, Rahmonqulov Temirbek Eshmamatovich	
AYOLLARNING YETAKCHILIK KOMPETENSIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI VA TO'SIQLARI	1088
Baymuratova Guldjahan Xamdamovna	
INVESTITSIYA FAOLIYATINI MUQOBIL MOLIYALASHTIRISH AMALIY TAHLILI JARAYONLARI.....	1093
Boboqulov Akmal Muborakbekovich	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOB, IQTISODIY TAHLIL VA AUDIT TIZIMLARINI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISH YO'NALISHLARI	1099
To'laganov Ziyovuddin Kamolitdin o'g'li	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT VA UNING IQTISODIY O'SISHDAGI AHMIYATI	1105
Nematullo Zuvaydullaev	

GLOBAL OZIQ-OVQAT TIZIMIDA AQSH IMPORT-EKSPORT SIYOSATI VA UNING MILLIY OZIQ-OVQAT XAVFSIZLIGIGA TA'SIRI	1109
Matjonov Bekjon Ravshonbekovich	
KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNING RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI ASOSIY OMILLAR VA IQTISODI SAMARADORLIGI TAHLILI	1115
Axatova Shahnoza	
ЭКОТУРИСТИЧЕСКИЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ И РЕСУРСЫ БУХАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ.....	1119
Каримова Фотима Абдурасуловна	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT: O'ZBEKISTONDA ELEKTRON SAVDO VA TO'LOV TIZIMLARINING RIVOJLANISHI.....	1124
Toxirov Shodibek Jo'ra o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA IPOTEKA KREDITLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA ILG'OR XORIJ TAJRIBALARI VA ULARNI O'ZBEKISTONDA QO'LLASH IMKONIYATLARI.....	1128
Tohirov Muhammad Bobur Tohir o'g'li	
KATTA HAJMLI MA'LUMOTLARDAN OVOZLI XABARLARNI AJRATIB OLIISHDA PARALLEL HISOBLASH ALGORITMLARI VA UNING DASTURIY MAJMUASINI ISHLAB CHIQUISH	1135
Jummayeva Yulduz Achilovna	
MAMLAKATDA NODAVLAT VA NOTIJORAT TASHKIOTLARNI MOLIYAVIY TA'MINLASH MEKANIZMLARI VA ULARNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	1141
Xusanova Gulsum Baxtiyorovna	
TURISTIK KORXONALARDA BREND KAPITALI TUSHUNCHASI VA UNING TARKIBIY ELEMENTLARI	1146
Zufarov Akmal Gulamiddinovich	
IPOTEKA KREDITLARINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING ILG'OR XORIJ TAJRIBALARI VA ULARNI O'ZBEKISTONDA QO'LLASH IMKONIYATLARI	1155
Rasulov Doniyor Dilmurod o'g'li	
RIVOJLANAYOTGAN MAMLAKATLARDA SOLIQQA TORTISHNING TARTIBGA SOLISH FUNKSIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA FISKAL SIYOSAT SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	1161
Sulaymonov Farrux Shuxratovich	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON AGRAR TARMOG'IDA TRANSFORMATSION O'ZGARISHLARNING INSTITUTSIONAL MEKANIZMLARI VA ULARNING SAMARADORLIGI.....	1166
Mambetnazarov Baxit Bisenbaevich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATI KORXONALARINI STRATEGIK BOSHQARISHNING DOLZARBLIGI	1171
Turg'unov Muxriddin Mo'ydinjon o'g'li	
TOSHKENT SHAHRIDA SHAHARSOZLIK JARAYONLARINING EKOLOGIK OQIBATLARI	1175
Ashurov Abdulaziz Rustamovich, Olimov Anvarjon Atamirzayevich	
O'ZBEKISTON TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATINING RIVOJLANISH DINAMIKASI VA UNDA XORIJIY INVESTITSIALARNING ROLI.....	1182
Nazarova A.N.	
XO'JALIK YURITUVCHI SUBYEKTLARDA MOLIYAVIY BOSHQARISHNING AYRIM JIHLTLARI.....	1187
Mamatov O'tkir Botir o'g'li	
JANUBI-G'ARBIY O'ZBEKISTONDA CHORVACHILIK TARMOQLARINI PROGNOZ QILISHNING GEOGRAFIK JIHLTLARI (NAVOIY VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	1191
Xudoyberdiyeva Iroda Abduxomidovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA DAVLAT MOLIYASINI BOSHQARISHDA G'AZNACHILIK TIZIMINI RAQAMLASHTIRISHNING MOLIYAVIY SAMARADORLIGI.....	1199
Tangrieva Farida Abdugarimovna	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI ISHLAB CHIQUARISH KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY BARQARORLIGIDA INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNING AHAMIYATI	1204
Kurbanova Shaxnoza Yuldashbayevna	
YASHIL MARKETING YONDASHUVI ORQALI KORXONALARDA RESURS SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	1211
Sapayev Axmed Durdibayevich	

АНАЛИЗ И ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ СЕБЕСТОИМОСТИ ПРОДУКЦИИ И РАСХОДОВ НА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ	1216
Ташмухамедова Карима Саматовна, Якубова Сабина Алишеровна	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA FERMER XO'JALIKLARINI SAMARALI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	1222
B.B.Seilbekov	
O'ZBEKISTONDA "YASHIL" IQTISODIYOT VA EKOLOGIK BARQARORLIK SIYOSATINI SHAKLLANTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	1226
Sadullayev Rasulbek Palvanbayevich	
ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF FOREIGN TRADE ACTIVITY IN UZBEKISTAN'S REGIONS AND FORECASTING REGIONAL FOREIGN TRADE UNDER WTO AND EAEU ACCESSION (BASED ON THE CASE OF KAZAKHSTAN).....	1230
Sitara Tojiqulova Sobirjon qizi	
BANKLARNING KREDIT RISKLARINI BAHOLASH VA NAZORAT QILISHNING – COST OF RISK (COR) KO'RSATKICHI TAHLILI	1240
Maxmudov Omon Tuxtayevich	
1-WIRE PROTOKOLI ASOSIDA BIOSIGNALLARNI UZATISH JARAYONI VA MA'LUMOTLAR STRUKTURASINI LOYIHALASH	1245
Mullajonova Fotima Tuychibayevna	
TIJORAT BANKLARI AKTIVLARINING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH BO'YICHA XORIJIY TAJIRIBA VA UNING XUSUSIYATLARI	1250
Ibrohimov Davronbek Muhammadi o'g'li	
ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА В МЕДИЦИНЕ.....	1257
Хамидходжаева Назира Махкамовна	
AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARI AYLANMA MABLAG'LARINI BOSHQARISH METODOLOGIYASI.....	1260
Taspanova Ayzada Kenjebayevna	
MAMLAKAT IQTISODIYOTIDA OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATI VA UNING RIVOJLANISH HOLATI	1264
Xusanova Gavhar	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA LTE VA NR TARMOQLARINING BIRGALIKDA ISHLASHINI TA'MINLASH YO'NALISHLARI.....	1270
Toshmatov Salohiddin Zayniddinovich	
THE OPPORTUNITIES OF PERSONALIZING TOURISM SERVICES THROUGH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE	1276
Olimov Davron Olimovich	
ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ РАДИОЖУРНАЛИСТИКИ В ЭПОХУ ЦИФРОВОГО ЭФИРА: ОПЫТ УЗБЕКИСТАНА И ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ	1281
Мамадалиева Шахноза Абдумаликовна	
EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF ADMINISTRATIVE PERSONNEL IN UZBEKISTAN'S PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES.....	1289
Inoyatov Orzubek Saidvaliyevich	
ZAMONAVIY MENEJMENTDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING O'RNI VA SAMARADORLIKKA TA'SIRI.....	1297
Igamberdiyeva Nasiba Babadjanovna	
DAVLAT QIMMATLI QOG'OZLARI MILLIY MOLIYA BOZORINI BARQARORLASHTIRISH OMILI SIFATIDA.....	1304
Rabiyev Akram Homitovich	
AKTSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARIDA INNOVATSION JARAYONLARNI KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV TIZIMI ASOSIDA TARTIBGA SOLISH ISTIQBOLLARI	1311
Xujaxonov Nuriddin Nasrullayevich	
ВОПРОСЫ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ И РАЗВИТИЯ ДИСТАНЦИОННОГО БАНКОВСКОГО ОБСЛУЖИВАНИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	1318
Худайберганава Зарофат Захидовна	
К ВОПРОСУ О РАССМОТРЕНИИ РИСКОВ ЛЕГАЛИЗАЦИИ НЕЗАКОННЫХ ДОХОДОВ В УЧЕБНЫХ МАТЕРИАЛАХ ПРОФИЛЬНЫХ ПРЕДМЕТОВ ПО БАНКОВСКОМУ АУДИТУ.....	1324
Мухамедова Севара Абдуллаевна	

MINTAQA SANOATIDA RAQAMLI XIZMATLAR BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIIYA JARAYONI	1336
Norov Murodjon Maxmudovich	
O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNI JALB QILISH: HOLATI, MUAMMOLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	1342
Maxkamov Otabek Muhammadjonovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA O'RTA VA UZOQ MUDDATLI DAVRDA DAVLAT QARZINI BOSHQARISHNING AMALDAGI HOLATI TAHLILI.....	1351
Egamberdiyev Jonibek O'ralovich	
OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARI O'RTASIDA RAQOBAT VA UNING MUAMMOLARI	1354
Mardonov Bahodir Bahronovich, Abdanov Rahmatillo Abdig'afurovich	
AHOLI BANDLIGINI TA'MINLASH HAMDA TURMUSH DARAJASINI OSHIRISHNING ISTIQBOLLI YO'NALISHLARI	1360
Xamdamiyev Shaxzod Ilhom o'g'li	
ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ МЕХАНИЗМ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННЫХ ВОЗМОЖНОСТЕЙ ДЛЯ РАЗВИТИЯ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН.....	1365
Дадабоева Муштари Хамидиллаевна	
SAVDO JARAYONIDA MARKETING TEXNOLOGIYALARINI QO'LLANILISHI	1371
Jalalova Dildora Jamolovna	
PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF GREEN FINANCING IN UZBEKISTAN: LESSONS FROM SOUTH KOREA.....	1375
Karshieva Marjona Alisher kizi	
TURIZM XIZMATLARI EKSPORTI VA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	1380
Qurbonova Malika Ahmad qizi	
SUN'IY INTELLEKT VA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISH YO'NALISHLARI	1384
Uzoqov Farhod G'afforovich	
SOLIQ MA'MURIYATCHILIGI MEKANIZMI VA UNING RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDAGI RIVOJLANISHI....	1388
Ibadullayev Sanjar Sodiqmuratovich	
BANKLARDA MUAMMOLI KREDITLAR BILAN ISHLASH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	1392
Mitillayev Ibrohimjon Tursunpulatovich	
BUG'DOY HOSILDORLIGI VA YALPI HOSILINI TAHLIL QILISH HAMDA HISOBLASH USULLARI	1396
Uzoqova Ziyodaxon Abdug'afforovna	
RAQAMLI MOLIYAVIY XIZMATLAR SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASHNING ZARURIYATI VA AHAMIYATI	1402
Muyassarzoda Fayziyeva	
MAKROIQTISODIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASH ORQALI AGRORESURLAR BOZORI IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI	1408
Aliyev Yashnarjon Egamberdiyevich, Tashmuxeimova Yayra Atxamovna	
JAHONDA KREATIV SOHALARNI RIVOJLANISH EVOLYUTSIYASI VA HOZIRGI DAVRDA IQTISODIYOTDA TUTGAN O'RNI.....	1414
Ismailov Azizbek Ruzimaxammatovich	
OSIYO DAVLATLARI RAQAMLI JURNALISTIKADA AYOLLAR ISHTIROKI (JANUBIY KOREYA, HINDISTON, YAPONIYA) DAGI ZIDDIYATLAR.....	1425
Zakirova Oisha	
ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ ОБЩЕСТВЕННОГО СОЗНАНИЯ В ЭПОХУ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА: СОЦИОЛОГИЯ РОЛИ ЖЕНЩИН И ГЕНДЕРНОЙ ИДЕНТИФИКАЦИИ В ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКОМ ОБЩЕСТВЕ	1431
Сиддикова Гулноза Абдумаликовна	
AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARIDA TOVAR-MODDIY ZAXIRALAR HISOBINI YURITISHDA TA'MINOT JARAYONINING AHAMIYATI.....	1437
Nuraliyeva B.	

TEMIR YO'L TRANSPORTI INFRATUZILMASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA RAQAMLI TEKNOLOGIYALARNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKKA TA'SIRI	1443
<i>Raximov Xasan Shukurjonovich</i>	
XALQARO TASHQI ISHLARDA KATTA MA'LUMOTLAR TAHLILI VA MA'LUMOT DIPLOMATIYASI: AXBOROTNI STRATEGIK RAZVEDKAGA AYLANTIRISH	1450
<i>Kurolov Maksud Obitovich</i>	
TALIM BOSHQARUVIDA "YASHIL KO'NIKMALAR"NI INTEGRATSIYALASH VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH: TALABALAR VA TIZIMLARNI IQLIM HARAKATIGA VA YASHIL IQTISODGA O'TISHGA TAYYORLASH.....	1460
<i>Esanova Shohida</i>	
НАЛОГОВАЯ КУЛЬТУРА: СУЩНОСТЬ, ПРОБЛЕМЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ОПЫТ	1468
<i>Хамзина Динара Рашатовна</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI SANOAT KORXONALARINING INNOVATSION FAOLIYATINI TANLANMA KUZATUV ASOSIDA O'RGANISH METODOLOGIYASI.....	1473
<i>Jalolov Ilhomjon Isomiddinovich</i>	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI KORXONALARIDA "YASHIL MENEJMENT" TIZIMINI JORIY ETISH	1482
<i>Masharipova Sevara Bekturdi qizi</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT RISKLARINI BOSHQARISHNING INNOVATSION USULLARI	1487
<i>Marimova Indira Rasul qizi</i>	
DAVLAT KORXONALARINI ISLOH QILISHNING ZAMONAVIY BOSQICHLARI VA O'ZBEKISTONNING XUSUSIYLASHTIRISH MODELII.....	1492
<i>Murodov Orif Jumayevich</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARNING RESURS BAZASINI MUSTAHKAMLASHNING XORIY TAJRIBASI	1497
<i>Sultanmuratova Dilrabo Shaylavbekovna</i>	
ЦИФРОВАЯ МОДЕРНИЗАЦИЯ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЁТА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ, ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ И ПУТИ ГАРМОНИЗАЦИИ С МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫМИ СТАНДАРТАМИ	1502
<i>Киличева Ф.Б.</i>	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNING MAKROIQTISODIY KO'RSATKICHLARGA TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH	1507
<i>Kurbanov Feruz Pirnazarovich, Quدراتov Islom Ismat o'g'li</i>	
ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ И ПРИОРИТЕТНЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ СФЕРЫ УСЛУГ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН	1511
<i>Маденова Эльмира Нзаматдиновна</i>	
ПРАВОВАЯ ПРИРОДА СОГЛАШЕНИЯ О РАЗДЕЛЕ ПРОДУКЦИИ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН	1516
<i>Мансуров Обид Зайнидинович</i>	
РЕКЛАМА ХИЗМАТЛАРИ BOZORIDA RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI OSHIRISHGA OID NAZARIY QARASHLAR.....	1522
<i>Xamrakulov Azamat Baxritdinovich</i>	
TIKUV-TRIKOTAJ KORXONALARDA VOSITACHILARNI MOTIVATSIYALASH MASALALARI.....	1528
<i>Jalilov Jamshid G'anjionovich</i>	
SOLIQ MA'MURIYATCHILIGI SUBEKTLARI O'RTASIDAGI O'ZARO HAMKORLIK MEKANIZMLARINING RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIGA MOS TRANSFORMATSIYASI	1534
<i>To'rayev Shavkat Shuxratovich, Ibadullayev Sanjar Sodiqmuratovich</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA KAMBAG'ALLIKNI QISQARTIRISH O'RTASIDAGI O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIK.....	1540
<i>Yaxshibayev Ulug'bek Shavkat o'g'li</i>	
THE IMPORTANCE OF SPOKEN ENGLISH IN GLOBAL COMMUNICATION	1545
<i>Dr. Mamatkulova Shohista Jalolovna</i>	
MAHALLIY DAVLAT ORGANLARINI RAQAMLASHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI	1549
<i>Nurmurodov Zafarjon Nurmurod o'g'li</i>	
IQTISODIYOTNI DEKARBONIZATSIYALASH: MOHIYATI VA IMKONIYATLARI.....	1554
<i>Xashimova Salima Nigmatullayevna</i>	

RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI ISHLAB CHIQUARISHNING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	1558
B.B.Mambetnazarov, Tureev Atabek Abatovich	
BUXORO VOHASINING MUSULMON ZIYORAT TURIZMI IMKONIYATLARINI BAHOLASH: ACES 3.0 METODIKASI ASOSIDAGI TAHLIL	1563
Kurbanova Mohinur Xabib qizi	
KICHIK KORXONALARDA ISHLAB CHIQUARISH OMILLARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING NAZARIY YONDASHUVLARI.....	1568
Mustafakulova Nodira Primovna	
BEVOSITA VA BILVOSITA SOLIQQA TORTISHNI OPTIMAL TASHKIL ETISH METODOLOGIYASI	1572
Qodirov Baxodir Qudratovich	
SUT VA SUT MAHSULOTLARI KORXONALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHNING USLUBIY JIHATLARI	1577
Normuradov Nurbek Sunatilloevich	
ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИЯ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЁТА И ЕЁ ВЛИЯНИЕ НА ВНУТРЕННИЙ АУДИТ В КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКАХ	1581
Шарахметов Шерзад Шаазимович	
O'ZBEKISTON "YASHIL" IQTISODIYOT SARI: QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI ENERGIYA MANBALARINING RIVOJLANISH METODLARI.....	1588
Qodirov Baxodir Tursunovich	
IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNING MOHIYATI VA MAZMUNI.....	1592
Feruz Mirzoyeva Salimovna	
YASHIL O'SISH, YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH: ATAMAVIY VA O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIK MASALASI.....	1597
Djalilov Sardor Sadilloevich	
YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNI QISQARTIRISHDA SOLIQ MA'MURCHILIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ORQALI DAROMAD VA XARAJATLARNI DEKLARASIYALASHNING TUTGAN O'RNI	1601
Mamatkulov Salimjon Raxmonkulovich	
DIGITAL ECONOMY AND GREEN TECHNOLOGIES: INNOVATIONS ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT	1606
Amiriddinova Madinabonu Zayniddin kizi	
FARG'ONA VODIYSIDA FAOLIYAT YURITAYOTGAN TO'QIMACHILIK KORXONALARINING EKSPORT SALOHİYATI TAHLILI VA ULARNI BAHOLASH	1609
Qodirov Humoyun Tolibjon o'g'li	
SIFAT VA RAQOBATBARDOSHLIK.....	1616
Xasanova Robiyaxon Kamoliddin qizi, Yuldashev Abduhakim Abdukarimovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA IPOTEKA KREDITLASH JARAYONINI TASHKIL ETISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI.....	1620
Mardiyev Akrom Djumaboyevich	
BIRLAMCHI TIBBIY-SANITARIYA MUASSASALARINI NATIJADORLIK INDIKATORLARI ASOSIDA MOLIYALASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	1627
S.J. Sultanov	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KOMPLAENS NAZORAT VA MOLIYAVIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA'MINLASHNING NAZARIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI	1633
Ulashbayev Shohruh Abdivoxobovich	
BIOMASSA ASOSIDA OZUQA ISHLAB CHIQUARISH ORQALI IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKGA ERISHISHNING AYRIM JIHATLARI	1639
Xazratkulov Niyoz Namazbayevich	
STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT OF CORPORATE TALENTS	1644
Shoyunusova Arofat, Sanjar Mirzaliev	
AGROTIZIMDA ANOR YETISHTIRISHNING O'RNI VA IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI	1648
Ortiqov Sulton Davronqul o'g'li	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATINI HOZIRGI KUNDAGI TAHLILI	1652
Mahmudova Chinora Anvar qizi	
XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNI JALB QILISHDA IMTIYOZLAR VA KAFOLATLAR TIZIMINING AHAMIYATI	1657
Nizamov Xusniddin Fazliddinovich	

SANOAT TARKIBIY O'ZGARISHLARINING IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHGA TA'SIRINING EKONOMETRIK TAHLILI (XORAZM VILOYATI MISOLIDA).....	1663
Jumaniyazov Nodirbek Odilbek o'g'li	
MINTAQAVIY RIVOJLANISH SHAROITIDA SHAHARLAR AGLOMERATSIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY JIHLTLARI.....	1670
Abdulkakimov Zuxrali Tursunaliyevich	
TIBBIY XIZMAT KO'RSATUVCHI KORXONALAR SAMARADORLIGINI IFODALOVCHI KO'RSATKICHLAR.....	1674
O'roqov Firdavs Ortiqniyoz o'g'li	
СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И МЕТОДЫ ФИНАНСОВОГО АНАЛИЗА В ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ АКЦИОНЕРНЫХ КОМПАНИЙ.....	1678
Бекбаева Феруза Бахтиеровна	
AUDITNING XALQARO STANDARTLARI ASOSIDA BUDJET BILAN HISOB-KITOBLAR AUDITINI TASHKIL QILISHNING AMALIY JIHLTLARI.....	1684
Rashidov Zuhridin Sanjar o'g'li	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA SOLIQ TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	1690
Radjabov Umurzoq Ablakulovich	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ ПРАКТИКИ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ВАЛЮТНЫМИ РИСКАМИ КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКОВ	1695
Тугалов Бобур Қаршибой угли	
DYUZDO SPORTIDA JAROHATLAR PROFILAKTIKASI VA TIBBIY TIKLANISH USULLARINING SAMARADORLIGI.....	1699
Tangriyev Abdullo Tovashovich	
HAVO TRANSPORTI ORQALI YUK TASHUVCHI TADBIRKORLIK SHAKLLARI VA UNDAGI MUOMMOLAR.....	1703
Anvarova Dilfuza Abdusattor qizi	
HUDUDIY IQTISODIYOTDA INNOVATSION SIYOSAT MEKANIZMINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING TIZIMLI MODELI	1709
G'aniyev Sanjar Poziljon o'g'li	
СОВРЕМЕННАЯ МОДЕЛЬ УЧЕТА ЗАТРАТ И АУДИТА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: НАЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ БАЗА И МСА.....	1716
Юлчиев Ойбек Улуғбек ўгли	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA YANGI BANK XIZMATLARINI JORIY ETISHDA HORIJYIY TAJRIBALARNI INTEGRATSIYALASH YO'LLARI.....	1723
Umarov Abdulquddus Abdilxatovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH DAVRIDA KICHIK BIZNES IMKONIYATLARINI KENGAYTIRISH.....	1731
Isroilov Dilshodbek Rustamovich, Isroilova Odina Rustambek qizi	
O'RMON XO'JALIGINI MOLIALASHTIRISHDA MOLIVAVIY RESURLAR VA MANBALAR.....	1737
Mamatqulova Muxlisa Mamirjanovna	
ZAMONAVIY JAHON IQTISODIYOTIDA OZIQ-OVQAT XAVFSIZLIGI, ISROFI VA YO'QOTISHLARINI KAMAYTIRISH MASALALARI.....	1743
Nazarova Gulbahor Raxmonkulovna	
KORXONA FOYDASI VA UNING RAQOBATBARDOSH NARX SIYOSATINI MAKSIMALLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	1748
Axmadjonov Murodjon Axadjon o'g'li	
DEVELOPMENT PRIORITIES FOR THE FRUIT AND VEGETABLE SECTOR IN THE CONTEXT OF UZBEKISTAN'S FOOD SECURITY POLICY	1754
Nazarova Munavvar Soatmurod qizi	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA HR MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ORQALI IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH IMKONIYATLARI	1761
Xamroyeva Kumush Alisherovna	
QURILISH SANOATIDA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH VA YASHIL IQTISODIYOT TAMOYILLARI.....	1768
G'ulomova Shaxlo Baxtiyor qizi	
TURISTIK DESTINATSIYA TUSHUNCHASINING NAZARIY-KONSEPTUAL ASOSLARI	1772
Bekberganov Izzat Hurmat o'g'li	
TRANSPORT XIZMATLARI BOZORI TUSHUNCHASI VA UNING IQTISODIYOTDAGI O'RNI.....	1775
Jo'rayeva Shahzoda Farhod qizi	
O'ZBEKISTONDA QURILISH MAXSULOTLARI ISHLAB CHIQRADIGAN KORXONALARNING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGI TAHLILI	1781
Yusufova Laylo G'ayrat qizi	

RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA BANK MAHSULOTLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH TENDENSIYALARI.....	1788
Xujamuratov Abbas Mardonovich	
PR-BO'LIMI FAOLIYATINI TASHKIL ETISHNING TARKIBIY-FUNKTSIONAL YONDASHUVLARI.....	1792
Ergasheva Fotimaxon Ibragimovna	
TURIZM XIZMATLARINI RIVOJLANISHINING O'ZIGA XOS TENDENSIYALARI	1797
Xujakulova Odina Valijonovna	
DAVLATNING IQTISODIY MUVOZANAT VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHDAGI ROLI.....	1805
Uzoqov Bekzod Bozor o'g'li	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA MAHALLIY MODA BRENDINI RIVOJLANTIRISH STRATEGIYALARI.....	1810
Tuxtayeva Oydinoy Normamatovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE IN UZBEKISTAN	1817
Sadinova Maqsuda Azamjonovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNING ISHSIZLIK DARAJASIGA TA'SIRINING EKONOMETRIK TAHLILI	1824
Raxmonov Bekzod Sharibjon o'g'li	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI BAHOLASHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI.....	1832
Djurayev Laziz Tursunboyevich	

DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE IN UZBEKISTAN

Sadinova Maqsuda Azamjonovna

Oriental University,
Department of Business and Management, Assistant

Abstract. This research examines how infrastructure development influences tourism demand in Uzbekistan — a nation strategically located in Central Asia with growing potential to become a key global tourism destination. In recent years, the country has witnessed an increase in both domestic and international tourist arrivals. The study primarily evaluates the impact of improvements in transportation systems, accommodation facilities, and digital services on regional tourism dynamics. By employing academic literature review, data analysis, and practical case examples, the research demonstrates that infrastructure development significantly enhances tourist satisfaction and accessibility to destinations. The findings indicate that the construction of new highways, modernization of airports, expansion of hotel capacities, and advancement of digital technologies have substantially contributed to the growth of tourist inflows.

Key words: Infrastructure development, Tourism demand, Uzbekistan, Transportation, Digitalization, Sustainable tourism.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot O'zbekistonda infratuzilmaning rivojlanishi turizm talabiga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishini o'rganadi. Markaziy Osiyoda strategik joylashgan ushbu davlat global turizmning asosiy manzillaridan biriga aylanish salohiyatiga ega. So'nggi yillarda mamlakatda mahalliy va xalqaro sayyohlar oqimi ortmoqda. Tadqiqotda transport tizimlari, joylashtirish (mehmonxona) obyektlari va raqamli xizmatlardagi o'zgarishlarning turizm dinamikasiga ta'siri baholangan. Ilmiy adabiyotlar, statistik tahlillar hamda amaliy misollar asosida o'tkazilgan tadqiqot natijalari infratuzilma rivojlanishi sayyohlar qoniqishini va manzillarga yetib borish imkoniyatlarini sezilarli darajada oshirayotganini ko'rsatadi. Xususan, yangi avtomobil yo'llarining qurilishi, aeroportlarning modernizatsiyasi, mehmonxona quvvatining kengaytirilishi va raqamli texnologiyalarning rivoji turizm oqimining oshishiga sabab bo'lmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: Infratuzilmani rivojlantirish, Turizm talabi, O'zbekiston, Transport, Raqamlashtirish, Barqaror turizm.

Аннотация. Данное исследование посвящено изучению влияния развития инфраструктуры на спрос в сфере туризма в Узбекистане — стране, стратегически расположенной в Центральной Азии и обладающей растущим потенциалом стать одним из ключевых мировых туристических направлений. В последние годы наблюдается увеличение числа как внутренних, так и иностранных туристов. В работе оценивается воздействие улучшений в транспортных системах, средствах размещения и цифровых сервисах на динамику туризма в регионе. На основе анализа научной литературы, статистических данных и практических примеров показано, что развитие инфраструктуры значительно повышает удовлетворённость туристов и доступность туристических объектов. Результаты исследования свидетельствуют, что строительство новых автомагистралей, модернизация аэропортов, расширение гостиничных мощностей и совершенствование цифровых технологий способствуют существенному росту туристических потоков.

Ключевые слова: Развитие инфраструктуры, Туристический спрос, Узбекистан, Транспорт, Цифровизация, Устойчивый туризм.

INTRODUCTION

Tourism, as one of the key sectors of the global economy, has demonstrated dynamic and sustained growth in recent years. In this regard, every nation strives to strengthen and diversify its tourism industry in line with its available resources, geographical advantages, and socio-economic potential. The expansion of the tourism sector not only stimulates national economic development but also fosters intercultural dialogue among peoples, generates employment opportunities, and contributes to the advancement of regional and local infrastructure.

The importance of tourism is particularly evident in countries such as Uzbekistan, which possesses an exceptionally rich historical, cultural, and architectural heritage. However, the presence of valuable historical monuments and diverse natural landscapes alone is insufficient to guarantee sustainable tourism development.

Achieving competitiveness in the modern tourism market requires the establishment and modernization of high-quality infrastructure — including transport networks, accommodation facilities, communication systems, catering services, accessibility to tourist attractions, and other supporting amenities (figure 1).

Figure 1. Tourism Infrastructure

Source: Author's compilation based on Zalunyna, O. (2020). Organization of the information field structure in the field of construction of tourist infrastructure. *Intellect XXI*, 1, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.32782/2415-8801/2020-1.7>

LITERATURE REVIEW

As Uzbekistan continues its economic liberalization and deepens structural reforms, the necessity to comprehensively assess national achievements, identify existing challenges, and enhance development strategies through the effective adaptation of advanced international experience becomes increasingly important. At the core of this ongoing progress lies the accelerated integration of Uzbekistan into the global economy and the consistent implementation of practical measures aimed at liberalizing foreign economic activities. One of the country's strategic priorities is the development of international tourism infrastructure that fully aligns with contemporary global standards and sustainable development principles.

This section provides a comprehensive overview of the theoretical foundations of tourism infrastructure development, examines the best practices of advanced nations, analyzes the current strengths and development prospects of Uzbekistan's tourism infrastructure, and presents conceptual perspectives on its transformation and modernization.

Theoretical evaluations of the role of infrastructure in economic growth are closely linked to classical and modern growth theories. For instance, Arrow and Kurz (1970) considered infrastructure as a form of public capital within their growth models. Barro (1990) later expanded this framework, analyzing public capital through the lens of endogenous growth theory. Further contributions were made by Futagami et al. (1993), who incorporated private capital accumulation into growth models, thereby broadening the understanding of infrastructure's long-term effects on productivity.

These conceptual frameworks are supported by extensive empirical evidence confirming the positive correlation between infrastructure investment and economic development. Influential studies by Aschauer (1989), Easterly and Rebelo (1993), the World Bank (1994), Sojoodi et al. (2012), and Palei (2015) demonstrate

that infrastructure serves as a key catalyst for sustainable economic expansion, technological innovation, and improved living standards. In this context, strengthening tourism-related infrastructure in Uzbekistan represents not only an economic necessity but also a strategic opportunity for integrating into the global tourism market.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological framework of this study is designed to comprehensively examine the impact of infrastructure development on tourism demand in Uzbekistan. The research employs a quantitative approach that integrates empirical analysis with statistical modeling to evaluate the relationship between infrastructure quality and tourism activity.

This section outlines the research design, data collection procedures, variable operationalization, econometric model specification, and estimation strategy applied in the study. The methodological approach ensures the reliability, validity, and objectivity of the results. Primary data were collected through structured surveys and official statistical sources, allowing for a systematic analysis of tourism-related indicators such as transportation accessibility, accommodation capacity, and digital service availability.

The econometric model was constructed to identify the direct and indirect effects of infrastructure development on tourism inflows, using regression-based estimation techniques. This approach enables a comprehensive understanding of how improvements in transportation, hospitality facilities, and digital infrastructure contribute to the growth of both domestic and international tourism in Uzbekistan.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

1. Research Design and Philosophy

This study adopts a positivist research philosophy, which assumes that social reality can be objectively measured, analyzed, and interpreted to identify causal relationships. The research design is primarily cross-sectional, relying on data collected at a single point in time to examine the associations between infrastructure development and tourism demand in Uzbekistan.

This design is appropriate for identifying correlations and testing hypotheses derived from economic growth theories regarding the determinants of tourism activity. The study employs an ordered probit model, which reflects the quantitative nature of the investigation and allows for the statistical evaluation of the hypothesized relationships between infrastructure, service quality, and tourism demand.

2. Data Source and Collection

The study sample consists of 107 respondents, representing both domestic and international tourists visiting various regions of Uzbekistan. The primary data were obtained through a structured survey titled "Tourist Infrastructure Survey in Uzbekistan."

The questionnaire was designed to collect detailed information about tourists' perceptions of the quality of infrastructure, services, and transportation, as well as their overall satisfaction and willingness to recommend or revisit Uzbekistan. The sampling strategy employed was convenience sampling, targeting tourists at key entry points, popular attractions, and major accommodation facilities across prominent tourist destinations such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, and Tashkent.

Data collection was carried out over several weeks to ensure diverse representation of visitors. Prior to the main survey, a pilot study was conducted with a small group of tourists to refine the questionnaire, ensure clarity of wording, and eliminate potential ambiguities. These steps enhanced the reliability and validity of the collected data. The finalized dataset (Tourist Infrastructure Survey in Uzbekistan.csv) was subsequently compiled and prepared for econometric analysis.

3. Variable Operationalization and Measurement

The operationalization of variables in this study is grounded in the theoretical framework linking infrastructure development to tourism demand.

Dependent Variable (y_i):

Tourism demand is represented as an ordinal variable reflecting respondents' likelihood of revisiting Uzbekistan or recommending it to others. It is categorized into five levels — Very Low, Low, Medium, High, and Very High. These categories correspond to threshold points (cut1, cut2, cut3, cut4) that separate different levels of perceived demand.

Latent Variable (y_i^*):

The observed ordinal variable is assumed to be driven by an unobserved continuous latent variable, y_i^* , representing the true level of tourism demand or satisfaction for each individual i . It follows a standard normal distribution, $\epsilon_i \sim N(0, 1)$. The categorical mapping is as follows:

$$y_i = \text{Category } 1 \text{ if } y_i^* \leq \text{cut1}$$

$y_i = \text{Category 2 if } \text{cut1} < y_i^* \leq \text{cut2}$
 $y_i = \text{Category 3 if } \text{cut2} < y_i^* \leq \text{cut3}$
 $y_i = \text{Category 4 if } \text{cut3} < y_i^* \leq \text{cut4}$
 $y_i = \text{Category 5 if } y_i^* > \text{cut4}$

Independent Variables:

Infrastructure (infra_i): Reflects perceptions of the quality and availability of tourism-related infrastructure (accommodation, amenities, roads, and internet access).

Service Quality (service_i): Measures the perceived quality of tourism services, including hospitality, efficiency of guides, restaurant service, and staff professionalism.

Transportation Accessibility and Quality (transport_i): Evaluates ease of access and quality of transportation modes, including international and domestic flights, public transport, taxi services, and road conditions.

All independent variables are measured using Likert-scale items and combined into composite indices to ensure internal consistency and analytical robustness.

4. Econometric Model Specification

The relationship between latent tourism demand (y_i^*) and the explanatory variables is specified using an ordered probit model, suitable for ordinal dependent variables. The model is defined as follows:

$$y_i^* = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{infra}_i + \beta_2 \text{service}_i + \beta_3 \text{transport}_i + \varepsilon_i, \quad \varepsilon_i \sim N(0, 1)$$

Where:

y_i^* – latent tourism demand propensity for individual i ;

β_0 – intercept term;

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ – estimated coefficients for infrastructure, service quality, and transportation accessibility, respectively;

ε_i – stochastic error term following a standard normal distribution with mean zero and variance one.

This model structure enables a rigorous examination of how improvements in infrastructure and service quality influence the likelihood of higher tourism demand categories.

5. Estimation Strategy and Interpretation

Model parameters — including coefficient estimates and threshold (cut point) values — are obtained using Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE). This approach identifies parameter values that maximize the likelihood of observing the actual sample data.

Estimation is performed using recognized statistical software such as Stata, R, or Python, ensuring computational precision and reproducibility. The coefficients derived from the ordered probit model indicate the direction and strength of each independent variable's influence on tourism demand.

The interpretation of the β coefficients in the ordered probit model requires a nuanced understanding, as it differs from linear regression analysis. A positive and statistically significant β coefficient for an independent variable indicates that an increase in that variable raises the likelihood of an individual being classified in a higher category of the latent variable (y_i^*), thereby increasing the probability of belonging to higher observed outcome categories — for instance, “High” or “Very High” levels of tourism demand.

To make the interpretation more intuitive, marginal effects were calculated. These effects measure the change in the probability of being in a particular outcome category (y_i) given a one-unit change in an independent variable, holding all other variables constant. The marginal effects are computed at the mean values of the explanatory variables, thereby providing a clear quantitative interpretation of each determinant's contribution to tourism demand.

6. Hypotheses

Based on the theoretical framework and research objectives, the following hypotheses were tested:

- H1: An improvement in tourism infrastructure quality (infra_i) has a significant positive impact on tourism demand (y_i^*) in Uzbekistan.
- H2: An improvement in tourism service quality (service_i) has a significant positive impact on tourism demand (y_i^*) in Uzbekistan.
- H3: An improvement in transportation accessibility and quality (transport_i) has a significant positive impact on tourism demand (y_i^*) in Uzbekistan.

7. Ethical Considerations

Ethical standards were strictly observed throughout the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring that they fully understood the purpose of the study, their right to withdraw at any stage, and the confidentiality of their responses. To guarantee anonymity, no personally identifiable information

was collected alongside survey data. All information has been securely stored and will be used exclusively for academic and analytical purposes. This approach ensured transparency, ethical integrity, and compliance with international research ethics norms.

8. Limitations

Although this study provides a robust methodological framework, certain limitations are acknowledged. The cross-sectional design restricts the ability to establish definitive causality, as data capture relationships at a single point in time. While the ordered probit model identifies directional associations, longitudinal datasets would further strengthen causal inference.

Additionally, reliance on self-reported survey data may introduce perception-based bias; however, the use of a pilot study, careful questionnaire design, and a statistically adequate sample mitigate these concerns. Future studies could complement these findings by incorporating objective infrastructure metrics or using multi-source triangulated data.

Despite these limitations, the methodological approach adopted in this research provides reliable and valuable insights into the relationship between infrastructure development and tourism demand in Uzbekistan, thereby supporting informed policy and investment decisions in the sector (table 1).

Table 1. Model Summary (Ordered Probit)

Variable	Coefficient (β)	Std. Error	z-value	p-value ($P> z $)
Infrastructure Quality	0.345	0.078	4.42	0.000
Service Quality	0.215	0.087	2.47	0.014
Transport Quality	0.151	0.068	2.22	0.026
cut1	-1.945	0.291	-	-
cut2	0.475	0.274	-	-
cut3	2.025	0.310	-	-

All coefficients are positive and statistically significant, indicating that improvements in infrastructure, service, and transportation quality substantially increase the probability of higher tourism satisfaction levels.

Interpretation of Findings

A one-unit increase in infrastructure quality raises the latent propensity for a higher tourist experience category by approximately 0.345 units ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, service quality and transport quality exhibit statistically significant positive effects ($p < 0.05$) (table 2).

Table 2. Predicted Probabilities (at Mean of X)

Outcome	Probability
P(Y = 1)	0.082
P(Y = 2)	0.188
P(Y = 3)	0.362
P(Y = 4)	0.275
P(Y = 5)	0.093

At the average level of infrastructure, service, and transport quality, the most probable tourist experience category is Category 3 ("Neutral/Average"), followed by Category 4 ("Good") (table 3).

Table 3. Average Marginal Effects at the Mean

Outcome	Infrastructure Quality	Service Quality	Transport Quality
P(Y = 1)	-0.0200	-0.0125	-0.0080
P(Y = 2)	-0.0405	-0.0260	-0.0175
P(Y = 3)	0.0050	0.0025	0.0015
P(Y = 4)	0.0380	0.0250	0.0150
P(Y = 5)	0.0175	0.0110	0.0090

For instance, a one-point increase in infrastructure quality enhances the probability of achieving a top-category ($Y = 5$) tourism experience by approximately 1.75 percentage points, while reducing the likelihood of lower satisfaction categories (table 4).

Table 4. VIF Diagnostics

Variable	VIF
Constant	1.00
Infrastructure Quality	1.45
Service Quality	1.38
Transport Quality	1.22

All Variance Inflation Factors (VIFs) are well below 5, indicating the absence of multicollinearity among independent variables, and confirming the model's statistical robustness.

Analysis of Infrastructure and Tourism Experience

The results of the ordered probit model comprehensively answer the central research question regarding the influence of infrastructure, service, and transport quality on tourism experience categories. The coefficient for infrastructure quality (0.345) demonstrates a strong and significant positive relationship with the latent variable representing overall tourist satisfaction.

A one-unit improvement in infrastructure shifts the probability distribution toward higher satisfaction levels, particularly increasing the likelihood of "Good" ($P(Y = 4)$) and "Excellent" ($P(Y = 5)$) experience categories from 30.8% to 36.8%. The marginal effect of +1.75 percentage points for the highest category confirms that better infrastructure directly enhances the probability of an excellent tourism experience.

2. The Impact of Infrastructural Development on Tourism Demand

Although the econometric model focuses primarily on tourist experience rather than aggregate arrival numbers, the quality of experience remains a key determinant of repeat visitation and positive word-of-mouth — both of which are fundamental drivers of tourism demand.

The observed shift in predicted probabilities — where $P(Y=1)$ decreases by 2.00 percentage points and $P(Y=5)$ increases by 1.75 percentage points for a one-unit improvement in infrastructure quality — clearly illustrates that enhancements in roads, utilities, and public amenities substantially reduce negative visitor experiences while increasing the frequency of peak satisfaction levels.

Satisfied visitors are more inclined to recommend destinations and to return for future visits. Therefore, sustained infrastructural development is expected to lead to higher occupancy rates, longer average stays, and increased tourism revenues over time. In the broader context, infrastructure serves as both a physical and psychological enabler of visitor comfort, safety, and accessibility, forming the backbone of sustainable tourism growth in Uzbekistan.

3. Key Dimensions of Infrastructure Influencing Visitor Satisfaction

The analysis identifies three main dimensions of infrastructure that have a statistically significant influence on overall visitor satisfaction:

- Infrastructure Quality ($\beta = 0.345$): Represents the condition and availability of physical assets such as roads, utilities, and public facilities.
- Service Quality ($\beta = 0.215$, $p = 0.014$): Reflects hospitality standards, accommodation quality, and efficiency of digital guest services such as online booking and feedback systems.
- Transport Quality ($\beta = 0.151$, $p = 0.026$): Captures the accessibility, reliability, and convenience of both public and private transport systems.

All three factors are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), confirming their joint importance in shaping visitor satisfaction. The service quality dimension accounts for approximately 62% of the impact magnitude of overall infrastructure, while transportation contributes about 44%.

This result suggests that, although core infrastructure remains the foundation of tourism competitiveness, targeted improvements in digital services, hospitality standards, and seamless intercity connectivity yield significant gains in visitor experience and satisfaction. Investments in user-friendly digital platforms, efficient hotel management systems, and integrated transport services would therefore amplify Uzbekistan's attractiveness as a modern tourism destination.

4. Regional Infrastructure Variations and Their Effects on Tourist Flow

While the current econometric model does not explicitly segment data by region, regional disparities in infrastructure quality can be inferred through variation in average scores. For example, if a particular region scores 1.5 points above the sample mean, the probability of achieving an "Excellent" tourism experience

increases by approximately 2.6 percentage points (1.5×1.75 pp). Conversely, regions performing below the mean may experience comparatively lower satisfaction levels.

A 0.5-point deficit in transport quality alone could reduce the likelihood of a top-tier experience by about 0.45 percentage points (0.5×0.90 pp), potentially affecting repeat visitation and destination competitiveness.

By mapping these marginal effects across provinces, policymakers and investors can identify underperforming regions where targeted infrastructural investments would yield the highest returns in terms of tourist retention, regional equity, and balanced economic growth.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of the study demonstrate that the enhancement of core infrastructure ensures the most substantial improvement in positive tourist experiences, while complementary investments in service quality and transport accessibility significantly strengthen this effect. Therefore, policymakers and regional planners are encouraged to adopt a comprehensive and integrated approach to tourism infrastructure development — one that unites physical modernization, hospitality enhancement, and mobility improvement — to stimulate tourism demand and guarantee balanced visitor distribution across all regions of Uzbekistan. The first research objective, “To determine the connection between visitor traffic and the quality of infrastructure,” has been effectively achieved. The findings confirm that infrastructure quality, particularly the condition of transport routes, hotel facilities, communication systems, and digital services, exerts a strong positive influence on tourist arrivals. Regions equipped with well-developed infrastructure demonstrate consistently higher tourist inflows, while superior service quality enhances overall satisfaction and increases the probability of repeat visits. Uzbekistan’s tourism sector is presently advancing toward a new phase of comprehensive infrastructure modernization, and to maintain this dynamic progress, it is crucial to capitalize on all available opportunities, attract both domestic and foreign investments, and ensure efficient coordination between public and private stakeholders. Issues related to accessibility and accommodation remain pivotal factors shaping the country’s image as a globally competitive destination, and to address these, it is advisable for the government to simplify visa and entry procedures, strengthen connectivity among major tourist destinations through modernized road and transport networks, and improve signage systems, navigation tools, and auxiliary infrastructure to enhance visitor orientation and comfort. Furthermore, it is recommended that the state diversify accommodation facilities to cater to the needs of various tourist categories — including budget travelers, business visitors, and premium clients — while the establishment of high-standard meeting and conference facilities, coupled with efficient and responsive service delivery, will reinforce hospitality quality and promote Uzbekistan’s image as a leading tourism hub. While the tourism industry continues to expand, limited trade opportunities and insufficient digital network accessibility constrain growth in certain regions; therefore, it is necessary to extend broadband internet coverage, advance digital infrastructure, and encourage private sector participation in the creation of technology-driven, visitor-friendly environments, which will enrich the overall travel experience, particularly for younger and tech-oriented tourists. In conclusion, for the successful and sustainable advancement of Uzbekistan’s tourism industry, large-scale investment in infrastructure modernization is indispensable, as a high-quality infrastructure base not only enhances service efficiency but also broadens the range of tourism products, particularly in remote areas with high development potential. Consequently, the joint efforts of government institutions and private investors are essential to strengthening the country’s tourism attractiveness, stimulating innovation, and positioning Uzbekistan as a competitive, safe, and globally integrated travel destination.

REFERENCES

1. Abubakirova, A., Syzdykova, A., Kelesbayev, D., Dandayeva, B., & Ermankulova, R. (2015). *Place of tourism in the economy of Kazakhstan Republic*. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 39, 3–6. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(16\)30232-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(16)30232-5)
2. Antonescu, D. (2014). *Regional development policy in context of Europe 2020 strategy*. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 15, 1091–1097. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(14\)00561-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(14)00561-9)
3. Arkhipova, V. F. (2006). *On infrastructure as a determining factor in the development of tourism in the region (Ob infrastrukture kak opredelyayushchem faktore razvitiya turizma v regione)*. pp. 42–44.
4. Arabov, N., Nasimov, D., Janzakov, B., Khomitov, K., Utemuratova, G., Abdurayimov, D., & Ismailov, B. (2024). *Shaping the future of Uzbekistan’s tourism: An in-depth analysis of infrastructure influence and strategic planning*. *Journal of Eastern European and Central Asian Research (JEECAR)*, 11(1), 53–65. <https://doi.org/10.15549/jeecar.v11i1.1478>
5. Beerli, A., & Martin, J. D. (2004). *A model of destination image formation*. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 31(3), 657–681.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 10

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

Ei.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>